

CROSS- SECTIONAL STUDY ON PREVALENCE OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE AMONG MARRIED WOMEN ATTENDING SELECTED PRIMARY HEALTH CENTRE PUDUCHERRY

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Domestic violence, also known as intimate partner violence, happens within intimate relationships. Domestic violence can take many different forms, including verbal, physical, and sexual abuse as well as threats of assault. **Aim of the study:** The main aim of the study to determine the prevalence of domestic violence among married women attending selected Primary Health Centre Puducherry. **Methodology:** The research approach adopted for this study was Quantitative research approach. Cross-sectional research design was used to for the study. The total sample size was 450 married women. The samples were selected using Purposive sampling technique. **Results:** The study level of domestic violence reveals that out of 450 subjects 245(54.44) subject experiences mild form of domestic violence, 65(14.4) of them had facing moderate form of domestic violence, 12(2.7) of them had faced severe form of domestic violence. Regarding the prevalence of domestic violence out of 450 subjects 249 (55.3 %) have reported domestic violence. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that the prevalence of domestic violence was found to be high in married women spouse with alcohol consumption, therefore it is evident that nearly half of the married women faced mild form of domestic violence in selected Primary Heath Centre in Puducherry.

Keyword: Domestic violence, Married women, Prevalance

INTRODUCTION

Human rights encompass various rights, including freedom from slavery, life and liberty, freedom of speech, job, and education, among others. Women are crucial societal figures, forming the foundation of families and contributing to neighborhood improvement. They often seek external assistance and improve family life quality. Domestic violence against women, which can take various forms, is the most common in India. It can endanger the victim's life, health, and development, and can cause physical harm, intimidation, and violence. Assessing the prevalence of domestic violence in specific areas is essential due to local social norms and women's literacy levels.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Domestic violence is a prevalent issue in many regions, including East Asia and Western Europe, with over 16% and 19% of women experiencing it respectively. Psychological violence is also a significant aspect of this problem, with 82% of women parliamentarians affected. In 2022, the National Commission for Women reported 30,900 crimes against women, with 6,900 involving domestic abuse. A recent study in India found that 29.3% of married Indian women aged 18-49 have experienced domestic or sexual abuse, and 3.1% of pregnant women experienced physical violence. Health personnel should provide support to women who have experienced domestic violence, empathize with their experiences, and seek appropriate services. Early research has contributed to understanding the causes of violence, its cycle, and its impact on children.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A Cross- Sectional study on prevalence of domestic violence among married women attending selected Primary Health Centre, Puducherry

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To determine the prevalence of domestic violence among married women attending selected Primary Health Centre Puducherry.
2. To find out the association between the level of domestic violence among married women with selected demographic variables.

ASSUMPTION:

Married women may have a risk of exposure to domestic violence

METHODOLOGY

The research approach adopted for this study was Quantitative research approach. The research design adopted for this study was cross-sectional survey research design. The study was conducted in Primary Health Centre, Puducherry.. The sample size for this study 450 married women who was selected using Purposive sampling technique. Inclusion criteria includes age group of above 18 years, Willing to participate in the study and those who are able to understand Tamil and English.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Six Primary Health Centre (PHC) were selected by using a simple random technique from 29 PHC in Puducherry. 75 subjects were selected from each PHC as per inclusion criteria by using purposive sampling technique. Total of 450 subject were selected from all Six PHC. Each day 15- 17 subjects were interviewed. The researcher spent 4-5 days to cover each PHC and maintained confidentiality for each subject. The researcher informed the subject to sit comfortably in separate room in PHC. For each subject data was collected by using standardized, self-administered structured 20 item domestic violence questionnaire developed by Dr. P. V. Indu (2011) to determine the prevalence of domestic violence. It takes 10- 15 minutes for each subject to complete the questionnaires. At the end of the data collection the researcher created awareness by distributing handout on Antidomestic violence act. The same procedure was followed for all 6 Primary Health Centre in Lawspet, Mettupalayam, Kosapalayam, Sorapet, Sedarapet and Sooramangalam.

MAJOR FINDING

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of demographic variables among married women

The results of the study reveal that the distribution of demographic variables, concerning age majority of 166(36.9%) were aged between 25 – 34 years. With respect to education, the majority 157(34.9%) had primary and middle school education. Regarding employment status 330(73.3%) were unemployed, With respect to religion 425(94.4%) were Hindus. With reference to the type of family 257(57.1%) belonged to the nuclear family. With reference to the age of marriage, 306(68%) got married at the age of ≥ 18 years. In the type of marriage 346(76.9%) had arranged marriage. With reference to marriage registration 312(69.3%) had registered their marriage. With regard to number of children 303(67.4%) had 1 – 2 children. In family income 177(39.3%) of the subject getting income between 5000 – 10000.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2: Percentage distribution of levels of domestic violence among married women

The study finding revealed that out of 450 subjects 245(54.44) subject experiences mild form of domestic violence, 65(14.4) of them had facing moderate form of domestic violence, 12(2.7) of them had faced severe form of domestic violence..

Figure 3: Mean and standard deviation of types of domestic violence among married women.

The study findings reveal the types of domestic violence as the mean and standard deviation of psychological domestic violence was (20.10+8.187) and mean and standard deviation of Physical domestic violence was (10.33+4.407). It infers that among 450 subjects comparing with physical violence, psychological violence is common among married women.

Figure 4: Percentage distribution of prevalence of domestic violence among married women.

The above figure shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the prevalence of domestic violence among married women. Out of 450 subjects 249(55.33%) of them suffered with domestic violence. The present study evident that there is a significant association between the level of domestic violence with selected demographic variable as age, education, religion, family type, marriage age among married women with $p < 0.001$ level. There is a significant association between the levels of domestic violence with demographic variable as employment status and number of children among married women with $p < 0.01$ level

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the prevalence of domestic violence was found to be high in married women spouse with alcohol consumption, therefore it is evident that nearly half of the married women faced mild form of domestic violence in selected Primary Health Centre in Puducherry. By adopting the Antidomestic violence act to protect married women from various types of domestic violence and motivate them to adopt various schemes and seek help policy available for married women to protect their rights and health.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. A similar study can be replicated in different setting with larger samples to validate and generalize the findings of the study
2. A similar study can be conducted in the form of qualitative study or longitudinal study.
3. Comparative study can be conducted between men and women

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